

Adding Value to Packaging Materials Using Affective Design

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Abstract

This paper qualitatively examines how affective design and kansei engineering is being used to make product packaging materials distinctive and design processes more effective. New product development processes are often characterised by the generation of proposals by product designers based on their experience and insight, which are then consumer tested. This subjective process is not always reliable: as many as eighty five percent of new supermarket products fail. Kansei engineering techniques offer the ability to quantify the relationships between product features and emotional engagement. It provides a rational, objective basis for making design decisions and can be used to establish design rules, within particular product contexts. For packaging companies, such as coatings, paper and textured injection moulding manufacturers, for whom the basis of competition is principally cost, the power of the technique goes beyond being able to make better final products. Affective design allows these companies to engage with product designers in a new way. Manufacturers can use affective design techniques to determine the likely emotional response of consumers to their packaging materials and actively promote their products for specific uses. In this way they can contribute to the design process, rather than merely passively providing samples from which product designers make a choice. Affective design has the potential to change the basis of competition for some packaging materials, and allow some suppliers to provide a distinctive service with high added value. The advantage to product designers is that packaging manufacturers could provide well-informed evidence to underpin choice of materials.

Keywords: Kansei engineering, packaging, affective design.

Life is hard for packaging suppliers

Consumer expectations have evolved interdependently with what manufacturers can supply, to point where product functionality is no longer the basis of competition. The consumer takes it for granted that a product will work, and work well. Two trends in consumer expectations that can be discerned since the late nineties: firstly, ‘innovation’ or ‘inventiveness’ appears to be something that many manufacturers have attempted to project about themselves; and secondly, manufacturers are addressing the way consumers engage emotionally with their products.

Consequently, product designers have had to look beyond product functionality in order to make their products distinctive in the market place. They have to design the product and its packaging so that it appeals to the consumer on the right emotional level. It is not enough that a shampoo cleans your hair: the life-cycle properties of the product must meet the

customers' sociological, physiological, psychological and ideological needs (Tiger 1992) from the point of purchase to the point of disposal, if they are to buy and keep buying the product. L'Oreal™, for example, make their brand distinctive by advertising the number of patents they have applied for. This responds to the consumers ideological and psychological needs.

Whilst it is acknowledged that consumers make purchase decisions based on their emotional engagement with products, the basis for competition in packaging materials is largely cost. This is because product manufacturers have a wide choice of packaging suppliers available who can meet their needs. Of course there are other constraints on materials other than cost, but these too can often be reduced to a cost component. For example, a manufacturing constraint on flow-wrap packaging for chocolate bars is how fast the material can be moved through a packaging machine, but this is something that can be directly measured by manufacturing cost.

When their products become commodities, and the basis of competition is cost, packaging manufacturers respond by cutting costs and by becoming innovative, in exactly the same way as manufacturers of consumer products have had to become innovative when faced with cost-based competition. Many packaging manufacturers have therefore become sources of innovation. Rather than wait for the product manufacturer to tell them what they need from packaging, packaging manufacturers have been proactively developing new ideas in an attempt to make their products distinctive and to increase their products' added-value. As a functional example, manufacturers of spirit bottles, rather than the beverage manufacturers themselves, have been leading the way in developing anti-counterfeiting devices.

When it comes to helping designers develop new materials to help consumers engage emotionally with products, the packaging manufacturers are at a disadvantage because they are far removed from the ultimate consumer and excluded from the loop between designer and brand owner. They do not necessarily know the brand owner's required brand equity or proposition, and they do not know how the designer will attempt to embody the requirements into the packaging solution. They are passive participants in the design process.

Packaging manufacturers' power in the design process would increase if they could supply information about their materials and processes that would help the brand owner and the

designer address their requirements. One way to do this would be to develop the ability to articulate how the properties of their materials complement the brand proposition or engage the customer. The challenge then becomes twofold: firstly, packaging manufacturers need to develop techniques to quantify the properties of their materials in emotional terms; and secondly, they need to learn how to articulate these properties in ways designers will understand.

Changing the design process

In existing packaging design processes, the responsibility for embodying the brand proposition into the design is very much the product designer's. The brand owner might develop a brief, attempting to articulate the brand values, for the designer to work from. Whilst much effort might go into developing the brief, and it might be based on the outcomes of consumer testing, the brief will still be quite subjective and open to interpretation. Hence, the development of solutions will depend on the creativity, skills and experience of the product designer. The solutions generated by the designer can be tested to a certain extent, using established consumer testing techniques, but the particular factors that elicit particular responses from respondents often remain elusive and the bases for making decisions about the product design remain subjective. This remains an iterative process in which the new solutions are generated and analysed. Whilst brand owners find it relatively easy to design for functionality and manufacturability, embedding brand recognition and market appeal into packaging remains an art. Perhaps as a consequence of this, as many as 85% of new supermarket own-branded products in the UK fail.

When choosing packaging materials within existing design processes, designers will be guided by the brief, and will attempt to choose materials that, whilst satisfying any manufacturing constraints that have to be taken into account, will project the brand proposition. Packaging materials are frequently chosen from sample packs or swatches that are produced by the companies that make the materials. For example, figure 1 shows a sample book of fine papers often used for cosmetics packaging, and figure 2 shows a sample of in-mould surface textures for injection moulded products. In existing design processes, the designer does not usually receive guidance from the materials' manufacturers about the likely effects of the packaging. Indeed, unless the packaging manufacturers have been educated in product design, it is unlikely that they will have the common vocabulary to articulate the

emotional effects of their materials. It appears that, only within the realm of colour does a common language and vocabulary exist: The meaning of ‘warm’ and ‘cool’ colours, for example, is widely understood, but the meaning of seemingly straightforward adjectives for textures such as ‘rough’ and ‘smooth’ is not necessarily clear without samples. Thus packaging manufacturers often remain as passive providers of materials, which designers select or not, based on their creative, experience and interpretation of the design brief.

Figure 1, Samples of in-mould surface textures

Figure 2, Sample of fine paper for cosmetics packaging

Kansei engineering (Nagamachi 1995) is providing a way for the manufacturers of packaging materials to become more proactive in the design process. Kansei engineering provides methods for establishing the relationships between product features and the emotions they elicit. It can be used at a product category level: for example, to answer questions such as what packaging features in personal-care products are associated with ‘contemporary’ and ‘vibrant’? Or it can be used to answer specific questions about a product, such as what are the best radii for the curves of a particular cosmetics bottle? Kansei techniques can be used to establish design rules for a particular brand and so can contribute to the synthesis of a product, and it can be used to test consumer delight once the design is completed.

Manufacturers of packaging materials with whom we have been working have been excited by kansei engineering, because it offers the potential to add value to their products by allowing them to be more engaged with the design process. It enables them to identify the properties of their materials in emotional terms and then articulate it in ways that product designers will find useful. In the new design process, manufacturers are able to test the emotional response of consumers to their materials and supply this information to designers who can use it to choose the most appropriate material for their application. Rather than make passive offerings of their standard materials to designers, manufacturers will be able to offer bespoke materials optimised for a particular brand or product. Rather than choose materials from samples packs, designers will be able to enter into a dialogue with manufacturers about their needs. The advantages for product designers is that manufacturers will be more responsive to their needs and will be able to offer packaging materials tuned for their particular applications.

An example – Specifying surface textures for cosmetics bottles

A study was undertaken to identify the specification of frosted-glass bottles for cosmetics. The basis of the study was to objectively measure people's subjective feelings on stroking roughened glass surfaces of cosmetics bottles, and how the feelings depend on the surface roughness. The objective was to obtain reliable, valid evidence for choosing one surface texture specification for the frosted-glass bottles over another.

The approach used was based on the self-report methods of kansei engineering (Nagamachi 1995). Kansei engineering provides methods for translating a consumer's feelings and image about a product into its design elements. It involves collecting adjectives describing peoples' feelings about the product features that are being investigated. Users representative of the required demographic group are then asked to rank a variety of real or virtual examples of the product against the adjectives on a Likert-like scale. Linear or non-linear multivariate regression methods, for example principal component and factor analysis or neural network methods, are then employed to identify the relationships between the product features and user feelings. Although kansei engineering has been applied widely in Japan, including to automotive interior layouts, ladies shoes, drinks containers and toiletry products, and applications are now appearing in the West, it has mostly been concerned with the visual senses of shape and colour.

This study had four components: 1) the selection of adjectives with which to describe the touch feelings, 2) the preparation of glass surfaces of different roughness, 3) psycho-physical testing and 4) analysis. The psycho-physical testing took place in a pilot and a main phase. In the pilot phase roughness was prepared on flat glass samples. In the main phase it was prepared on bottles used for cosmetics.

An initial selection of adjectives was obtained from a focus group study. Fifteen cosmetics containers were collected. These were plastic, glass, metal and cardboard bottles, tubes and compacts used for eye makeup, moisturising cream, foundation powder, perfume, shower gel and lipstick. A surface sample of each container was mounted inside a test box so that it could be touched and stroked by inserting a finger through a slot formed in the face of the box. The purpose of this was to remove influences other than touch for determining the adjectives. Nine women, aged eighteen to forty, were invited to handle these and, after discussing their instinctive feelings, preferences and dislikes about the surfaces, some thirty two adjectives were collected. Further words were found in cosmetic catalogues and fashion magazines and from discussion with cosmetics' packaging technologists.

A flat plate glass was cut into five coupons (Figure 3b) and five clear glass bottles, of square section and rounded edges (Figure 3c) were obtained. Different surface finishes were produced on these, principally by grit blasting with alumina. The finishes were measured by contact surface profilometry. In a subsidiary test, a cast was made of a finger tip. Non-

contacting surface profilometry was used to compare the finger tip's roughness to the roughness of the glass surfaces.

In a pilot study, five differently finished glass flats were mounted in the test boxes (Figure 3a) and twenty two women, aged eighteen to forty were asked to record their feelings about touching and stoking each surface. They were asked to record their responses on a questionnaire based on 7-point semantic differential scale of opposing adjectives.

Figure 3, (a) sample test box; (b) and (c) flat and bottle test samples

In the main study, a further forty women similarly recorded their feelings from touching the surfaces of the five differently finished glass bottles. In this test, the bottles were in full view and the women were told that the bottles were for cosmetics. It was hypothesised that, as all the bottles were identical except for their surface finish, any influences of vision would be the same for all bottles, so differences in response might be attributed to differences of finish.

Principal component analysis was undertaken to establish an emotional semantic space into which the adjectival words used in the study could be loaded and to assign emotional positions or scores to the rough surfaces, within the same space. Relations were then sought between the surface emotional scores and the physically measured roughnesses.

This study highlighted some relationships between emotional engagement and surface roughness in the context of glass bottles for cosmetics. These experiments and their principal component analysis demonstrated that some adjectives, including in our experiments, feminine, smooth, tasteful and peaceful, do depend on surface roughness whilst others do not. When the surfaces' principal component scores were compared to their roughness, a neutral

feeling was found to correspond to roughness values (R_a) from 2 μm to 4 μm . The results of the study suggested that a positive feeling is gained from rubbing a surface that is smoother than a finger tip and a negative feeling from one that is rougher. The study therefore suggested that to evoke feelings complementary to the product, the surface roughness of the frosted-glass bottles should be less than about 2 μm .

Summary

Kansei engineering techniques offer the ability to quantify the relationships between product features and emotional engagement. It provides a rational, objective basis for making design decisions and can be used to establish design rules, within particular product contexts.

Manufacturers can use affective design techniques to determine the likely emotional response of consumers to their packaging materials and actively promote their products for specific uses. In this way they can contribute to the design process, rather than merely passively providing samples from which product designers make a choice. A kansei study was carried out to determine the specification for the roughness of frosted-glass cosmetics bottles.

Respondents were asked to rate grit blasted plate glass and bottles on a semantic differential questionnaire of opposing adjectives. In parallel, profilometry techniques were used to measure the surface roughnesses of the glass samples. Principal components analysis and regression techniques were then used to identify relationships between the roughnesses of the glass samples and the emotions elicited by them. The results suggest that a positive feeling is gained from rubbing a surface that is smoother than a finger tip and a negative feeling from one that is rougher. This study illustrates how kansei techniques can be used by manufacturers of packaging materials to assist in the design process by providing well-informed evidence to underpin choice of materials.

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